

Effects of Shade Treatments on Vine Growth and Production of Tubers and Propagules of Japanese Yam (*Dioscorea Japonica*) in Tea Gardens

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Abstract

*Tea gardens have specific light and shade conditions because the tea trees are densely planted, with only a narrow space between rows. Therefore, in practice, the variety of weeds that grow in tea gardens is limited. Japanese yam (*Dioscorea japonica*) is a serious weed that grows under shade conditions in tea gardens. This study investigated the effects of shade conditions on the growth of Japanese yam vines and the production of tubers and propagules. We observed that shading did not limit the growth of Japanese yam vines that emerged from the tubers, and even under strong shading conditions of 0% relative irradiance, vines of Japanese yam were able to grow more than 2 m. Furthermore, although the formation of new tubers and production of propagules were limited under strong shading conditions, they were not limited under 50% relative irradiance. Since the relative irradiance at 10 cm below the canopy after harvesting in this study was 65 %, there is concern that Japanese yam produces propagules even under the canopy of tea plants. On the other hand, the plants from tubers emerged and reached the canopy of tea trees earlier than those from propagules. This suggests that differences in emergence time and growth speed of vines between plants from tubers and propagules may be a factor in prolonging the duration of weeding Japanese yams.*

Keywords: Japanese yam (*Dioscorea japonica*), vine weed, tea garden, propagule

INTRODUCTION

Intensity of light is one of the most important environmental factors affecting plant growth (Cavagnaro and Trione, 2007; Dai et al., 2009; Cai, 2011; Deng et al., 2012). Therefore, understanding the growth and reproduction of weed species under shading conditions is

fundamental in developing weed control methods. Therefore, so far, various studies have been conducted on the relationship between weeds under shading treatments (Williams, 1970; Noguchi and Nakayama, 1978; Knake, 1972; Terasawa et al., 1981; Murphy and Gossett, 1981; Asano, 2001; Colbach et al., 2019).

Competition for light is the most serious cause of crop damage due to weeds. However, competition with weeds for light does not immediately affect tea trees because tea trees are perpetual, and the size of tea plants is larger than that of weed plants. On the contrary, the area under the tea trees is under shade conditions because the tea trees are densely planted, with only a narrow space between the rows. Therefore, in practice, the variety of weeds that grow in tea gardens is limited (Ichihara et al., 2020; 2022).

Dioscorea japonica (Japanese yam) is one of the most serious weeds in Japanese tea gardens (Seo, 2012; Ichihara et al., 2020). Japanese yam is a perennial plant widely found in forest margins and woodlands in Japan (Hori, 1984). Although Japanese yam has long been traditionally collected from natural habitats and used as food, recently, people have started cultivating it as a local crop (Iida, 2001). However, Japanese yam has become a serious weed in tea gardens.

Most weeds require ample sunlight for growth; however, Japanese yam grows in tea gardens with strong shade conditions, and the reason for this remains unclear.

In addition, although the ridge under the tea tree is strongly shaded by the leaf layers of tea trees, the illumination under the tea trees increases when the tea leaves are harvested. Therefore, the area under tea trees experiences a special lighting environment, with alternating light and shade conditions throughout the year. In this study, we investigated the effects of different light conditions on the growth of Japanese yams by changing the shading conditions to obtain basic information on the response of Japanese yams to light intensity.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area

This study was conducted in a test field and tea garden at the Center for Education and Research in Field Sciences, Shizuoka University (Kariyado, Fujieda city, Shizuoka Prefecture, Japan; 34°54'18.8" N, 138°16'19.7" E).

Relative illumination under tea trees

Relative irradiance trends were investigated at the ground level, in the middle of the tea plant (30

cm height), and at a depth of 10 cm below the canopy (50 cm height) from April 24 to June 5, 2020.

Growth of Japanese yam in the tea garden

This experiment was conducted in the tea garden at the Center for Education and Research in Field Sciences, Shizuoka University, where ‘*Yabukita*’ tea has been cultivated using conventional farming methods since 1974. Propagules (10 mm diameter) and tubers (average weight of 47.5 g and approximately 20 cm in length) obtained from Japanese yam propagules cultivated for one year were used in the experiment. On April 6, 2020, five propagules and five tubers were buried in the test field, in the area under the tea trees, at 30 cm intervals. The emergence time and vine length were determined for each plant twice a week.

Growth of Japanese yam under different shade conditions

This experiment was conducted in the test field for vegetables at the Center for Education and Research in Field Sciences, Shizuoka University. Propagules (10 mm diameter) and tubers (average weight of 47.5 g and approximately 20 cm in length) obtained from Japanese yam propagules cultivated for one year were used in the experiment. On April 6, 2020, five propagules and five tubers were buried in the test field at 30 cm intervals, and three posts were erected for the vines to wrap around. Six test plots were established according to differences in relative irradiance: 0 % irradiance (dark condition), 5 %, 10 %, 50 %, 50 % polarized, and 100 % (unshaded). Relative irradiance was adjusted by covering the plants with a black cheesecloth. The 50 % polarized was covered with a polarizing net (‘Passlite Blue’; Unitika, Tokyo) that absorbs red light in order to reproduce the light environment of the forest floor, which is shielded by the upper leaf layer. The emergence time and vine length were determined for each plant twice a week.

The test was terminated when most of the plants exceeded the 1 m height of the posts. The test was terminated on May 29, 2020, for the plants from tubers and on July 20, 2020, for the plant from propagules. As the plants from propagules produced new tubers and propagules, the number of propagules and the weight of new tubers of plants from propagules were measured at the end of the test on July 20.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Relative illumination under tea trees and the growth of Japanese yams in the tea garden

Fig. 1 shows the relative irradiance in the tea garden and the vine lengths of the Japanese yam from tubers and propagules. Relative irradiance before the first tea harvest was less than 5 % both at

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the ground level and in the middle of tea trees and 14 % at 10 cm below the canopy. Since it was reported that relative irradiance under the canopy of a typical orchard is estimated to be 10–80 % (Ito et al., 1987), our results indicate that the relative irradiance under the tea tree is considerably lower than in typical orchards. Relative irradiance increased after the first harvest; relative irradiance was 18% at the ground level, 28% in the middle, and 65% at 10 cm below the canopy. Relative irradiance then decreased with the growth of the tea buds after harvest, and on June 5, 40 days after the first harvest, the relative irradiance was the same as that before harvest.

Japanese yam plants from tubers emerged under tea trees after the first harvest, from May 8 to May 29, 2020, under the conditions of 10–20 % relative irradiance. In contrast, Japanese yam plants from propagules emerged from May 15 to June 8, that is, later than the emergence of plants from tubers. Plants from propagules emerged after the relative irradiance at the ground level decreased to less than 10 %. It is considered that this difference in emergence time between plants from tubers and plants from propagules causes the prolonged emergence of Japanese yams in tea gardens.

Our previous study reported that two types of plants emerge from propagules: the ‘elongation type,’ which extends vines, and the ‘floor type,’ which does not extend vines (Inagaki and Ishiwata, 2022).

In this experiment, three of the five plants from propagules were ‘floor type’. The two ‘elongation type’ plants had vine lengths of 81 cm and 70 cm, respectively, and their heights did not exceed 60 cm (the height of the tea tree canopy). Therefore, it is considered that vines from propagules have less chance of contaminating the tea leaves at harvest.

Growth of Japanese yam under different shading conditions

All plants from tubers extended vines regardless of the differences in shade conditions (Table 1). Three of five plants were ‘floor type’ under 5 % relative irradiance (Table 1). Similarly, three of five plants were ‘floor type’ in the tea garden with a relative irradiance of 10–20 % (Table 1). These results suggest that ‘floor type’ plants occur under strong shading conditions.

Fig.2 depicts the growth of vines after emergence from tubers and from propagules in different relative irradiance conditions. In the unshaded and polarized light plots, the earliest vines from tubers emerged in April. In all experimental plots, most of the vines emerged from early to late May. As in the results of the tea garden, in all experimental plots, plants from propagules tended to emerge later than plants from tubers. Furthermore, in all experimental plots, the plants from tubers

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grew faster after emergence and reached the canopy (height of 60 cm) earlier than the 'elongation type' plants from propagules. In contrast, the 'elongation type' plants from propagules reached the canopy of tea trees later than those from tubers. In Japanese tea gardens, control of Japanese yam is mainly performed by managing vines that have grown beyond the canopy of tea trees (Seo, 2012; Seo, 2016). This suggests that differences in emergence time and growth speed of vines between plants from tubers and propagules may be a factor in prolonging the duration of weeding Japanese yams. Regardless of the difference in shade conditions, the vines from tubers elongated, and even under relative irradiance of 0 % (dark conditions), the vines grew to over 200 cm in length.

Japanese yam plants from tubers did not produce new tubers or propagules by the end of the test on May 29, whereas plants from propagules produced new tubers and propagules by the end of the test on July 20. Fig.3 shows the weight of old tubers and new tubers and the number of propagules of the elongating type formed from the propagules. The weight of old tubers increased as the shade increased. In contrast, the weight of new tubers increased as the shade decreased. Therefore, it is suggested that lower shade promotes the consumption of old tubers and the formation of new tubers. Extremely small new tubers were formed in plots with 10 % and 5 % relative irradiance, and no new tubers were formed in plots with 0 % relative irradiance (dark condition).

The results for new propagule formation were similar to those for new tuber formation; the number of propagules was the largest in the unshaded plots, and the propagule formation decreased as the shading increased (Fig.3). Only one of the five plants produced propagules at 10% relative irradiance. There were no propagules at 0 % and 5 % relative irradiance. Although the growth of tubers and formation of propagules in Japanese yam were suppressed under shaded conditions, the growth of tubers and production of propagules were observed under 50% relative irradiance. Since the relative irradiance at 10 cm below the canopy after harvesting in this study was 65 %, there is concern that Japanese yam produces propagule even under the canopy of tea plants.

On the other hand, the number of propagules produced under the 50 % polarized light conditions was the second largest, after that produced under the unshaded condition (Fig.3. In addition, the number of propagules under 50 % polarization was more than that under 50 % relative irradiance. The 50% polarization experiment plot reproduced the condition in which red light is absorbed from the light transmitted from the leaves, reducing the ratio of red light (R) to far-red light (FR) (R/FR ratio). Therefore, light transmitted from tea leaves may promote propagule

production in Japanese yam.

CONCLUSION

Japanese yams grow under the strong shade conditions of tea gardens. So far, the relationship between shading conditions and the growth of Japanese yam was unclear. However, this study demonstrated that shading conditions did not limit the growth of Japanese yam vines that emerged from tubers, and even under strong shading conditions of 0 % relative irradiance, Japanese yam vines were able to grow more than 2 m. Competition for light is the main competition between weeds and crops, and suppression of weed growth by shading of weeds by crop leaves is one of the strategies in weed management. However, in tea gardens, it is difficult to suppress the growth of Japanese yam using the shade created by tea trees.

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Fig.1 Changes in the relative irradiance in the tea garden and the vine lengths of Japanese yam from tubers and propagules.

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Fig.2 Growth of vines under different shade conditions

The thick black lines represent vines from tubers, the gray lines represent vines from propagules, and the dotted black line represents the height of the canopy (60 cm)

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Fig.3 Weight of old tubers (a) and new tubers (b) and the number of propagules (c) of the elongating type produced from propagules.

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Table 1 Percentage of 'elongation type' and 'floor type' plants formed from propagules under different shading conditions (%)

relative irradiance	elongation type	floor type
100 % (unshaded)	100.0	0.0
50 % polarized	100.0	0.0
50 %	100.0	0.0
10 %	100.0	0.0
5 %	40.0	60.0
0 % (dark condition)	100.0	0.0
tea garden	40.0	60.0